

From Innovation to Implementation: Driving Acceptance of 3Rs-Aligned Technologies

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Abstract

As the scientific community continues to prioritize ethical and human-relevant research, the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) remain central to advancing scientific innovation and animal welfare. Emerging technologies such as microphysiological systems (MPS), artificial intelligence, and digital biomarkers are powerful tools that enhance translational relevance while aligning with the 3Rs. However, despite their promise, widespread adoption remains limited due to behavioral, institutional, and regulatory barriers.

The 3Rs Collaborative, a U.S.-based nonprofit, is actively addressing these challenges by applying a scientific theory of human behavior change and fostering strategic, cross-sector working groups. Through this approach, we aim to accelerate the acceptance and integration of 3Rs-aligned technologies across research, industry, and regulatory landscapes. In this session, attendees will learn about efforts to advance these technologies including learning about the 3Rs Collaborative's ambitious cross-platform project with the U.S. FDA evaluating the use of MPS for DILI applications that involves 9 commercial developers.